

Solving a Traveling Salesman Problem with a Flower Structure

Gabriele Martino

Rome, Italy

Email: martino.gabri@gmail.com

Received 26 April 2014; revised 26 May 2014; accepted 2 June 2014

Copyright © 2014 by author and Scientific Research Publishing Inc.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Open Access

Abstract

This works aims to give an answer to the problem $P = NP$? The result is positive with the criteria that solve the Traveling Salesman Problem in polynomial cost of the input size and a proof is given. This problem gets a solution because a polyhedron, with a cut flower looking, is introduced instead of graph (e.g. tree).

Keywords

Traveling Salesman Problem, Polyhedron, Flower, NP-Complete

1. Introduction

The traveling salesman problem (TSP) has origin in 1832 in a hand book of Hamilton. It is a NP-complete problem and NP-hard problem and till now only some special cases are found to be polynomially executable with a reducible Turing machine. I propose a method which solves the general case in polynomial cost of the input size. To today I read [1], an annealing algorithm about TSP [2], and about the bottleneck TSP but I have also the opportunity to read [3] about another NP-complete problem, the job shop scheduling, with which I measure the size of NP problem. This problem and consequent solution are really important for industry.

Problem Definition and Notations

The TSP can be defined like the problem for salesman to go through each cities a, b, c, ..., v, z passing once on them and returning the shortest travel distance $S = w_1 + \dots + w_n$ as the sum of the weight of the arcs joining cities that are visited.

2. Method

Consider a polyhedron. Cities are disposed on the axis, so a, b, c, ..., z are positions on the axis of the cities from

a common origin in the space (a center) and therefore cities are on vertex of polyhedron (the limit of 26 letter doesn't mean limit of 26 cities, that's valid to all functions involved). The distance between two cities is the weight of the arc joining them. A cycle on the polyhedron that pass once on each city is a flower with the corolla as origin (center) and the coordinate axis of cities petals. To find a, b, ..., x, z we must solve the linear system for each variable that define the position on axis:

$$\begin{aligned}w_{ab} &= \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \\w_{ac} &= \sqrt{a^2 + c^2} \\&\dots \\w_{az} &= \sqrt{a^2 + z^2} \\&\dots \\w_{xz} &= \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}.\end{aligned}$$

The equation for node a is $W_a = w_{ab}^2 + w_{ac}^2 + \dots + w_{az}^2 = (N-1) \cdot a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + \dots + z^2$. We compute W_k ; $a \leq k \leq z$ having N variable in N equations and obtain a^2 will give easy access to a .

2.1. Theorem

Be O the set of petals. Be x the minimum and $O_1 = O \setminus \{x\}$ then $m_k = \min O_k$; $M_k = \min O_k \setminus \{m_k\}$; $O_{k+1} = O_k \setminus \{m_k, M_k\}$. The optimal sequence for petals is given by

$$\dots, m_3, m_2, m_1, x, M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots \quad (1)$$

2.2. Proof

In this section we will consider the petals a, b, c, ... as variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

$$\begin{aligned}\min S &= \min \left\{ \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2} + \sqrt{x_2^2 + x_3^2} + \sqrt{x_3^2 + x_4^2} + \dots + \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_n^2} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ f(x_1, x_2) + f(x_2, x_3) + f(x_3, x_4) + \dots + f(x_1, x_n) \right\} = \min \sum f\end{aligned} \quad (A)$$

Consider an inequality on functions for the swap of two elements

$$f(x_a, x_b) + f(x_c, x_d) + f(x_e, x_f) + \dots < f(x_a, x_c) + f(x_b, x_d) + f(x_e, x_f) + \dots \quad (B)$$

$f(x_a, x_b) - f(x_a, x_c) + f(x_c, x_d) - f(x_b, x_d) < 0$ with $\frac{\partial f(x, y)}{\partial x} = \frac{2x}{f(x, y)}$ so with equality of Δx the df

is higher at lower y , therefore if $x_a < x_d$ with $x_b < x_c$. Further consider that $f(x_a, x_b) + f(x_c, x_d)$ must be satisfied from one value of x_a, x_b to one value of x_c, x_d and therefore $x_a < x_c$ and $x_b < x_d$ is a stronger relation together with $x_a < x_d$ and $x_b < x_c$. So x_a, x_b minimum with x_c, x_d maximum with a complete satisfy condition is the lowest: $\{x_i, x_j\}_{\in f_1} < \{x_h, x_k\}_{\in f_2}$. This condition can be extended to more than two

elements so for example $f(x_a, x_b) + f(x_c, x_d) + f(x_e, x_f)$ minimum if $\{x_i, x_j\}_{\in f_1} < \{x_h, x_k\}_{\in f_2} < \{x_m, x_n\}_{\in f_3}$ (Optimality Condition OC 1).

2.2.1. Case of Four Dimensions

So if we have $\{x_1, x_2\}, \{x_2, x_3\}, \{x_3, x_4\}, \{x_4, x_1\}$ we start from the maximum $x_4 > x_{j=1,2,3}$ so that for condition OC 1 $x_{i=3} > x_{j=1,2}$ and $x_{i=1} > x_{j=2,3}$. The swap of x_1 with x_3 is indifferent because we have not prevalent constrains so solutions are $x_2 < x_1 < x_3 < x_4$ and $x_2 < x_3 < x_1 < x_4$. Those are symmetric respect to the minimum.

2.2.2. Case of More Dimensions

So if we have $A_1 := \{x_1, x_2\}, \{x_2, x_3\}, \{x_3, x_4\}, \{x_4, x_5\}, \{x_5, x_6\}, \{x_6, x_1\}$. In such sets we start from the maximum $x_6 > x_{j=1,2,\dots,5}$ so that, for condition OC 1, elements $x_5 > x_{j=1,\dots,4}$ and $x_1 > x_{i=2,\dots,4,5}$ are maximum. Here we will find only a symmetric solution considering $x_5 > x_1$. Further $x_5 > x_{j=1,2,3,4}$ therefore, for condition OC 1, $x_4 > x_{i=1,2,3}$ from the confront of others elements not sequenced; so we have to choose the order for x_4, x_1 , but $x_4 < x_1$ because notice that we have an even number of elements, two at high adjacent values $\{x_4, x_5\}, \{x_6, x_1\}$ and two at lower adjacent values $\{x_3, x_4\}, \{x_1, x_2\}$; the behaviour of down level $\{x_1, x_2\}, \{x_2, x_3\}, \{x_3, x_4\}$ is symmetric and specular of the choice of up level; the down level can have a good move symmetrically equivalent from uplevel choice whereas the uplevel depends on the choice, and so is convenient to have a good choice at up level (Optimality Condition OC 2). Further $x_1 > x_{j=2,3,4}$ and therefore, for condition OC 1, $x_2 > x_{3,4}$ but, for condition OC 2, $x_4 > x_2$. So the sequence became $x_3 < x_2 < x_4 < x_1 < x_5 < x_6$, with $\{x_2, x_3\}$ minimum.

So the order is the best solution. Therefore the solution with elements at right and left of the minimum in n-dimensions case is $x < m_1 < M_1 < m_2 < M_2 < m_3 < M_3 \dots$ that for symmetry is the same than $x < M_1 < m_1 < M_2 < m_2 < M_3 < m_3 < \dots$. Then (1) is true.

2.3. Algorithm

Node: a list of nodes

$w: NXN \rightarrow R$

Solve the linear system for a, b, ..., z obtain node

```

While result.size( ) < N do
  minimum = ∞ ;
  for i = 0 → i < N
    if node[i] < minimum ∧ i ∉ result then
      minimum = node[i];
      next = i ;
    end if
  end for
  if result.size( )mod2 ≡ 0 then
    result.add (position(last),next);
  else if result.size( )mod2 ≡ 1 then
    result.add (position(init),next);
  else if
  end while

```

Test

The algorithm has been tested on several instances 9×9 and in all of them the best solution is found in few seconds.

3. Complexity

The linear system can be found in $O(N^3)$ with Gauss method [4] whereas the cycle is $O(N^2)$ so the method is of $O(N^3)$. Then P = NP.

4. Discussion

The complexity can be reduced also changing the criteria to achieve an objective.

References

- [1] Ruohonen, K. (2013) Graph Theory.
- [2] Ming, Y.-K., Sanghi, M. and Bernstein, D.J. (2006) An Approximation Algorithm for Bottleneck Traveling Salesman Problem. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, **3998**, 223-235.
- [3] Carlier, J. and Pinson, E. (1989) An Algorithm for Solving the Job-Shop Problem. *Management Science*, **35**, 164-176.
- [4] Estatico, C. (2012) Sistemi Lineari: Algoritmo di Gauss, Lecture Notes Based on Notes of Prof. Marco Gaviano. University of Genova, Genova.
- [5] Santini, G. and Varsi, A. (2010/2011) Algoritmi Iterativi per sistemi lineari ed equazioni non lineari. University of Cagliari, Cagliari.

Appendix

Method to Solve the Linear System, Jacobi

$Ax = b$ with x vector of solution and b vector of constant terms. Choose $A = P - N$ so that P easy to invert. With $x^{(k+1)} = P^{-1}Nx^{(k)} + P^{-1}b$ and stop condition dependent from τ that must be tuned depending for example from the minimum x : $|x^{(k)} - x^{(k-1)}| < \tau |x^{(k)}|$ [5].

Scientific Research Publishing (SCIRP) is one of the largest Open Access journal publishers. It is currently publishing more than 200 open access, online, peer-reviewed journals covering a wide range of academic disciplines. SCIRP serves the worldwide academic communities and contributes to the progress and application of science with its publication.

Other selected journals from SCIRP are listed as below. Submit your manuscript to us via either submit@scirp.org or [Online Submission Portal](#).

